

LANGUAGE EXPRESSIONS ASSOCIATED WITH PROFESSIONALISM

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Annotation: The application of a cognitive-communicative strategy to teaching non-linguistic students foreign languages is the topic of this article. In order to get optimal communication efficiency, we ought to examine the speaker's speaking approach in this regard. Acknowledging the significance of context in a foreign professional discourse highlights how crucial pragmatic procedures are to its analysis and cognitive components. When teaching professional speech in a foreign language, this fact should be considered. Proficiency in the mental professional lexicon is defined as one of its formation's conditions.

Keywords: language culture, language culture theory, intertextuality, actual language, conceptual worldview, and professionalism.

Writing in the technical and scientific domains requires the use of specialized words. Every specialty or field generally employs a vocabulary that uses technical terminology to communicate a range of specific notions. These specialized phrases express condensed meanings that have developed over many years of subject matter study. The way each phrase distills a vast amount of information into a single word is what gives a specialized group of terms their worth. Technical language is frequently seen as shorthand, a means of conveying ideas accurately and deeply while using few words. Technical phrases are frequently easily incorporated into mathematical formulas and operations; for example, a term like force can be folded into a calculation like $f = ma$. This measurement enables the idea to be manipulated mathematically.

Professionalism is a seemingly vague term that you've never given much thought to in the past. But now that you're getting closer to launching a professional career, however, this word has taken on a lot more significance. You're about to be on the hunt for a new job in your career field, and you're aware that professionalism is a trait managers will be looking for in your interviews. You know that professionalism matters, but you still have some questions about this characteristic. *Why* is professionalism important, and what can you do to be more professional?

We spoke with HR specialists and hiring managers to get the answers you're looking for. These experts are sharing their experiences from the opposite side of the interview table, with insights on the importance of professionalism and how to act in a professional manner as you enter the workforce.

What is professionalism?

Simply put, professionalism is the way you conduct yourself at work to represent both yourself and your company in a positive way. It includes standards for behavior that might be mandated in an employee handbook, like adhering to a certain dress code, as well as traits that are harder to pin down but still valuable to being professional in the workplace.

Professionalism goes beyond a checklist of requirements. Instead, it includes "embodying the company's values and serving as a stellar representative of the company," according to Eric Mochnacz, HR consultant at **Red Clover**. "Professionalism is someone's inherent ability to do what is expected of them and deliver quality work because they are driven to do so."

The importance of professionalism. The experts agree that professionalism is one of the biggest factors in your level of career success. It might sound dramatic, but it's true! This trait affects every aspect of how you do your job. A lack of professionalism can cost you a job or promotion, and it can even put you first in line for a layoff.

"Your level of professionalism can make or break your career," Walker says. "Without it, you will never be taken seriously and you may even be looked over when it comes time to be considered for a promotion."

One reason professionalism is so important is because it's an outward display of your attitude toward your job and your company. "It's a sign of loyalty, dependability and responsibility," says Nate Masterson, HR manager at **Maple Holistics**. "A lack of professionalism suggests a lack of respect towards an employer, which can impact your ability to land a job."

Signs of professionalism. It's clear that professionalism is important, but what are the real-life signs of professionalism employers are looking for? Our experts have shared the examples of professionalism that are sure to catch their eye.

Despite terms numbering a great quantity, they are used by fewer people and therefore are not included into the general vocabulary. As the result terms are more constant and are, to a lesser degree, subjected to any morphological or semantic changes than the vocabulary of the every-day use. Most researchers admit that terminology is one of the main features of the scientific style, informative core of the science language.

Terms are traditionally defined as words, compound words or word-combination used in specific contexts. In order to define correctly the concepts expressed with terms it is necessary to know the field of science or technology to which this term can be referred. Each term must be considered in connection with the words around it and the context in general, because a term is a word which acquires a definite meaning according to the field of its use in a particular case. Terminological meaning of a word is usually unchangeable but it can be revealed only in the context. Terms are combined into systems of terms (terminology systems) that can be defined as a number of terms with fixed relations between them which reflect, in their turn, the relations between concepts that these terms designate.

A term has the same **functions** as any word does: **nominative** (nomination; i.e. naming the things), **significative** (generalization), **communicative** (communication), **pragmatic** (a function that indicates an attitude of a speaker to the things said or written). There are a number of terms classifications in modern linguistics. They are based on different features of a term or aspects of their study.

In the vocabulary of a scientific / technical text one can find two main categories of terms:

- terms of a certain sphere / field that have their own definition / meaning in it;
- generally scientific terminological units (including terms of interbranch sciences), for example, widely-used terms of philosophy, political science, mathematics, philology, etc.

Terms of the first category can be, in its turn, divided into three groups: **normative terms (nomenclature); professional terms (professionalisms); professional jargonisms.**

Normative terms, or nomenclature, are words that denote specific concepts and conform to all norms and requirements for national and borrowed terms: *absorption, accountability, flux, time constant, waste* etc);

Professional terms (professionalisms) are words and word-combinations that nominate a concept but do not reveal its complete meaning, they are comprehensible mostly for professionals.

Unlike nomenclature units, **professional terms** can be interpreted. Thus **professionalisms**, as the term itself signifies, are the words used in a definite trade, profession, or a name used by people connected by common interests both at work and at home. Professional words name anew already existing concepts and have the typical properties of a special code, but they do not aim at secrecy. They perform a socially useful function in communication, facilitating a quick and adequate grasp of the message. The main feature of a professionalism is its technicality. Professionalisms are special words in the non-literary layer of the English vocabulary, whereas terms are a specialised group belonging to the literary layer of words. Terms, if they are connected with a field or branch of science or technique well-known to ordinary people, are easily decoded and enter the neutral stratum of the vocabulary. Professionalisms generally remain in circulation within a certain community, as they are linked to a common occupation and social interests. The semantic structure of the term is usually transparent and is therefore easily understood. The semantic structure of a professionalism is often dimmed by the image on which the meaning of the professionalism is

based, particularly when the features of the object in question reflect the process of work, metaphorically or metonymically. Like terms, professionalisms do not allow any polysemy, they are monosemantic. Here are some professionalisms used in different spheres of activity: *tin-fish* (submarine), *piper* (a specialist who decorates pastry with the use of a cream pipe); *a midder case* (a midwifery case); *outer* (a knockout blow). Some professionalisms, however, like certain terms, become popular and gradually lose their professional flavour; **Professional jargonisms** do not require accuracy or monosemanticity. They are also figurative to a great extent and emotionally coloured; **jargonisms** are a periphery of terminological vocabulary which are used in speaking and are not regulated by and are often not fixed in the dictionaries. Professionalisms should not be mixed up with jargonisms. Unlike normative and professional terms, jargonisms aim at secrecy (*hammer* – local anesthetic, *chippie* – carpenter, *mudslinger* - calumniator, slanderer). Specialized vocabulary is most important and most widely spread in technical texts because it is most informative.

Though when using specialized terms, it is necessary to observe the following:

Match terminology to the ability of the audience. You may use a term with great accuracy and still not reach your audience. It is important that you be aware of your audience's level of understanding. If they are not experts in your field, you will need to substitute more general terms for your specialized terms. That means that you may not be able to write with great accuracy about your topic.

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